

Overall study design

Title of the study	Lipidomic Studies Reveal Specific Circulating Phosphatidylcholines as Surrogate Biomarkers of Omega-3 Index		
Document creation date	09/12/2023	Corresponding Email	britz@mcmaster.ca
Principle investigator	Philip Britz-McKibbin	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	McMaster University	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	MTBE
pH adjustment	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	Low resolution
Separation type 1	Capillary electrophoresis	Resolution at MS1	Low
Separation mode 1 (generic)	Multisegment injection-Nonaqueous Capillary Electrophoresis-Mass Spectrometry	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.001
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	QTOF	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	10000
MS vendor	Agilent	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
Ion source	ESI	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS1, MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool, Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	This study is linked to an accompanying method paper (revisions requested) that focused on validation of the assay that is also available as a pre-print on ChemRxiv (10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-0x35f) and cited.

Sample Descriptions

Randomized Placebo-controlled High-dose Fish Oil Supplementation Trial / Human / Serum

Provided information	-	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Randomized Placebo-controlled High-dose EPA and DHA Supplementation Trial / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PC[M+2HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Molecular species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+2HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragment name			
FA(16:0)			
FA(22:6)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	De Novo Annotation of Two PC Species Associated with the Omega-3 Index by MS/MS
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	As we employed a methylation derivatization step on serum/plasma ether extracts, all PCs were analyzed as their methylphosphate esters to enhance ionization response and improve separation (by NACE).
Background check at MS2	Yes		

1) PC[M+2HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Type I isotope correction	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Normalization to reference	No
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 16:0[D62]			
Type of quantification	Calibration line	Lipid Quantification Software	Mass Hunter
Type of calibration line	Solvent based	Batch correction	No
Species calibration line	PC 16:0_22:6	Further quantification remarks	All lipid extracts were methylation prior to MSI-NACE-MS analyses
Response correction	No		

2) PC[M+2HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+2HCOO]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragment name			
FA 16:0			
FA 20:5			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	De novo annotation of MS/MS spectra
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS1	No	Further identification remarks	No access to purified lipid standard.
Background check at MS2	No		

2) PC[M+2HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Mass Hunter
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC16:0[D62]			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	Response model	Further quantification remarks	Estimated response of PC 16:0_20:5 based on closest surrogate lipid
Type I isotope correction	No		